

Materials of International University Scientific Forum

Practice Oriented Science:
UAE – RUSSIA – INDIA

Part 1

June 17, 2022

UAE

Proceedings of the International University Scientific
Forum “**Practice Oriented Science: UAE – RUSSIA
– INDIA**”. Part 1

(June 17, 2022. UAE)

ISBN 978-5-905695-87-5

These Conference Proceedings combine materials of the conference – research papers and thesis reports of scientific workers. They examines technical and sociological aspects of research issues. Some articles deal with theoretical and methodological approaches and principles of research questions of personality professionalization.

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ISBN 978-5-905695-87-5

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IDENTIFICATION OF COMPETITIVE ADVANTAGES IN THE IMPLEMENTATION OF SECTORAL IMPORT SUBSTITUTION STRATEGIES

Ermakova Yasmin Maratovna

Researcher

Larin Sergey Nikolaevich

Lead Research Officer, Candidate of Technical Sciences,

Khrustalev Evgeny Yurievich

Head Research Officer, Doctor of Economic Sciences,

Central Economics and Mathematics Institute, RAS, Moscow, Russia

Abstract. *To ensure the development of the Russian economy in the face of sanctions pressure, its leading industries should rely on their competitive advantages. On the one hand, they can provide retaliatory sanctions, and on the other hand, implement sectoral import substitution strategies. The main purpose of this study is to identify competitive advantages that can be put into practice within the framework of sectoral import substitution strategies. System analysis and an integrated approach, as well as the main provisions of economic theory, were used as research methods. As a result of the research, it was found that import substitution strategies in Russian conditions have a number of features. They determine the industry competitive advantages in the implementation and are disclosed in the work in relation to the enterprises of the engineering industry. It is concluded that in order to ensure the development of the Russian economy, an effective innovative structure is needed for both manufacturing and extractive industries, as well as the use of technological resources of the defense industry for the development of general civilian production.*

Keywords: *sanctions restrictions, import substitution, industry strategies, competitive advantages, implementation mechanisms.*

Introduction

The illegality of the sanctions restrictions imposed by Western countries against Russia is extremely clear and understandable to everyone today. Such measures can in no way be attributed to the procedures of market regulation of the

economy. On the contrary, the main focus of sanctions restrictions is to contain and stifle the development of the Russian economy in every possible way, which in the era of globalization is clearly perceived as an expression of an undeclared, but widespread war, in the areas of trade, finance, information communications, and many others. And this is already tantamount to a desire to solve political problems through sanctions restrictions for the economy of one country - Russia, whose actions in the international arena are increasingly and more and more reasonably contrary to the desires of the world domination of the United States and its allies. At the same time, none of the developed countries is embarrassed to support the essentially illegitimate introduction of ever new sanctions restrictions, carried out without the sanction of the UN Security Council against a country that is its permanent member, as well as one of the initiators of the creation of the UN.

It is clear that in such a situation, Russia could not but respond to the unfriendly actions of many Western countries. This response was the introduction of targeted sanctions against certain industries and specific enterprises. However, a more serious response was the development and implementation of sectoral strategies for import substitution and programs for the accelerated development of industrial production as part of them. At the same time, their developers were well aware that the introduction of retaliatory sanctions could not become the main incentive for the development of the Russian economy. On the contrary, for this it will be necessary to replace the existing mechanisms for the formation of macro-economic policy with more effective tools for innovative development, allowing you to quickly change the structure of the entire economy of the country [1, 2].

Purpose of the study

The main purpose of this study is to identify competitive advantages that can be put into practice within the framework of sectoral import substitution strategies. Its implementation will allow the Russian economy to quickly determine the key imperatives for its development in the near future. And also to develop and implement a set of measures within the framework of sectoral import substitution strategies aimed at minimizing the negative impact of sanctions restrictions on the development of the Russian economy.

Research methods and materials

The continuation of the policy of sanctions restrictions will significantly destabilize the entire global economic system, since no one, up to their initiators, can adequately assess the expected damage to the Russian economy. Back in 2014, Barack Obama, as President of the United States, stated that thanks to the introduction of sanctions restrictions, the Russian economy would be "torn to shreds". However, the president has changed, the US-led policy of sanctions continues to tighten, and the Russian economy has managed to resist and, moreover, has shown modest growth over the past few years. From this, only one conclusion can be

drawn - the situation with the introduction of sanctions restrictions against the Russian economy once again confirmed the historical experience, according to which sanctions have never contributed to the achievement of political goals. On the contrary, with a high degree of probability, they can become a catalyst for a new global economic crisis or a local military conflict with unpredictable consequences. It is this version of the development of the situation that takes place today in Ukraine.

A characteristic feature of modern sanctions restrictions has become the impossibility of a sufficiently accurate determination of the costs, both for the country against which they are directed, and for the countries that acted as their initiators. Practice shows that in any case, losses, and quite significant ones, will be forced to be borne by all participants in the sanctions war. However, the ability to extract certain benefits from the introduction of sanctions restrictions may be more valuable here. Western countries have not yet been able to do this, but Russia has managed to respond quickly enough to a number of components and minimize the negative impact of sanctions restrictions on the country's economy. Thus, the imposed sanctions restrictions actually contributed to the completion of the creation of the national payment system. In the leading sectors of the economy, import substitution strategies have been developed and are currently being implemented in practice [3; 603]. In addition, measures were promptly introduced at the government level to support the leading sectors of domestic production. In addition, retaliatory targeted sanctions have been adopted. They are directed against certain industries and enterprises of those countries that have imposed sanctions restrictions against Russia.

As a result of these actions, a certain positive effect was obtained, due to which the Russian economy achieved a slight increase in production. However, expectations of its significant increase only due to sanctions restrictions do not stand up to criticism, since there are a number of other restrictions on the growth of the Russian economy. First of all, these are the low level of manufacturability of industrial production at many enterprises of the leading sectors of the economy, the lack of the necessary volumes of innovative production capacities, significant restrictions on attracting foreign investment and insufficient own investment resources [5; 95].

Practice has shown that defense industry enterprises continue to be potential drivers of the development of the Russian economy. It was in these industries that import substitution strategies were developed, the implementation of which ensured the maintenance of the defense capability of our country at the proper level. This direction was the main one, since it created favorable conditions for the implementation of import substitution strategies in other sectors of the Russian economy [6; 21]. Under the conditions of a significant limitation and complete cessation of import deliveries of the relevant equipment and components, Russian enterprises were forced to reorient their production to the production of their

domestic counterparts, which are not inferior in quality to foreign originals. The limitation of the possibility of the purchase of modern technologies by Russian enterprises by Western countries has led to the fact that in most industries producing civilian products, import substitution strategies have become inherently stochastic. At the same time, the number of industries in which import substitution strategies need to be implemented in the first place includes space activities, nuclear energy, microelectronics, transport and power engineering [7; 51].

Enterprises of the machine-building industry ensure the implementation of the innovative component of the development of the domestic economy and have a significant impact on the development of enterprises in other industries. The introduction of an innovative model for the development of the machine-building industry in modern conditions is becoming one of the promising ways to increase the competitiveness of the Russian economy in the international arena.

When implementing import substitution strategies in these and other industries, first of all, enterprises with a completely closed production cycle will be supported, because only they will be able to ensure the production of domestic products, the quality of which will meet international standards. Only after this will it become possible to create an internal market for the products of the engineering industry, based on detailed, subject, functional and technological specialization. In the short term, it is necessary to develop detailed specialization, but the future of the engineering industry is likely to be based on the dominance of a combination of functional and technological specialization. At the same time, detailed and subject specializations will also be preserved where necessary.

To reduce dependence on foreign equipment, it is necessary to increase the localization of domestic production. This can be done in two ways. The first is the development of the so-called "screwdriver production", for which domestic enterprises produce certain components. The second way is based on the manufacture of our own products, for the production of which imported components are purchased. In the first case, the localization of production does not determine the strategy for the development of the industry. In the second case, on the contrary, it is the localization of production that determines the strategy of sectoral development and the corresponding option for import substitution [4; 621]. It is on this path of development that Russia should orient itself. In addition, the localization of production in the defense industries, as well as in relation to dual-use products in space activities, will give the necessary impetus to the development of civilian sectors of the economy.

Results and discussion

As a result of the research, it was found that import substitution strategies in Russian conditions have a number of features that determine industry competitive advantages in their implementation. The main ones are the following.

1. Enterprises of the machine-building industry of the Russian economy, like most enterprises of other industries engaged in manufacturing, showed a short-term increase in exports of manufactured products only in the late 1990s after the devaluation of the national currency and in the second half of the 2000s after the global financial and economic crisis. During the same periods of time, there was a significant decrease in the possibilities of imports, which entailed forced import substitution for individual manufacturing enterprises of manufacturing industries. However, over the past 20 years, the coefficient of structural independence of manufacturing industries, in particular at the enterprises of the engineering industry, has continued to decline. As a result of this process, there was an increase in the dependence of domestic production on the purchase of imported equipment and components, and the "import infrastructure" of the engineering industry was formed and deployed.

2. The growth in purchases of imported equipment and components leads to the displacement of domestic products from the Russian market. With a further increase in prices, the demand for imported products decreases, but an increase in prices inevitably affects the fall in demand for domestic products. In this case, two fundamentally different mechanisms come into play. The first of them is that, depending on the supply of imported products and components, enterprises of the machine-building industry are forced to raise prices for their own products with an increase in prices for imported components. The essence of the second mechanism is that with a general increase in prices, it is necessary to increase the level of wages, rents and profits, but at the same time, the high dependence of aggregate consumption within the country on imported goods will reduce the price elasticity of demand for imported products and components and increase it by income. In addition, the increase in prices can be significantly multiplied due to the length of speculative supply and service chains for imported products and components in the domestic market.

3. If the structure of national consumption is dominated by imported products and components, then even an increase in exports of low-level domestic products (value added) will not ensure a long-term increase in wages. Thus, price increases worsen purchasing power parity, and price parity entails a decrease in income even from commodity exports. Therefore, one of the main directions for the development of the Russian economy should be the production of equipment and components for the raw materials industries, the agro-industrial complex, which should be able to provide the population of our country with high-quality food in the required volumes. This direction of development of the Russian economy will become the main competitive advantage of its industries in the long term.

Other competitive advantages of the development of the sectors of the real sector of the Russian economy in the face of the negative impact of sanctions restric-

tions and the implementation of import substitution strategies are seen as follows.

1. The development strategy for the sectors of the real sector of the Russian economy should be built on the basis of its structural restructuring.

The Russian economy has sectors (financial, banking, services that extract raw materials and other resources) with a high level of profitability and wages with low risks of conducting core business. At the same time, the Russian economy also has other industries (machine-building, manufacturing, etc.) in which the level of profitability is not high, and the risks of conducting core activities are quite high. To overcome such a structural imbalance, it is necessary to direct structural adjustment at the sectoral level of the economy to reduce the difference in the levels of profitability and risks between all sectors of the Russian economy.

2. To stimulate investment in the real sector of the economy, it is advisable to attract banking resources while reducing and differentiating interest rates across sectors.

This approach will make it possible to vary the prices of attracted credit resources, taking into account the solution of problems within the framework of sectoral import substitution strategies in various sectors of the Russian economy.

3. It is possible to stimulate the production of science-intensive products by reinvesting profits by channeling them into the development and expansion of capacities in the manufacturing industries of the machine-building industry.

In addition, a regression tax on profits can be introduced if it is directed to investments in the renewal of fixed assets of domestic industries.

4. When implementing import substitution strategies at enterprises of the military-industrial complex, it is necessary to achieve one hundred percent completion of the production of Russian weapons and military equipment with equipment, components and auxiliary units with the placement of a state defense order at domestic enterprises.

It is necessary to use all available resources to develop technologies that are not produced in Russia, or organize their replacement from countries that have not imposed sanctions against our country, or from countries that are their sole producers, using means of technical intelligence or industrial espionage through third countries.

5. To maintain the proper quality of mass-produced domestic products, it is necessary to develop a system of protectionist measures as part of the implementation of sectoral import substitution strategies.

With further tightening of sanctions restrictions, which, in fact, is currently happening, Russian enterprises that fall under their negative influence may freeze or restructure their obligations to pay external debt, if any. An equally important factor in obtaining competitive advantages as a result of the implementation of sectoral import substitution strategies can be the development of new financial

institutions within the framework of intercountry alliances (SCO, BRICS, etc.) in order to redistribute foreign exchange reserves, as well as the creation of a full-fledged national payment system.

Conclusions

Thus, for the strategic development of the Russian economy it is important:

- 1) focus on stimulating its restructuring and solving production and technological problems of introducing innovations in the framework of solving the problems of import substitution;
- 2) sanctions restrictions should be considered only a response, and not the main measure of strategic development.
- 3) to ensure the development of the Russian economy, an effective innovative structure is needed for both manufacturing and extractive industries, as well as the use of technological resources of the defense industry for the development of general civilian production.

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